

Hyperion

D9.4 Information packs for referenced and networked communication amplifiers

Deliverable number	D9.4
Deliverable title	Information Packs for referenced and networked communication amplifiers
Nature ¹	R
Dissemination Level ²	PU
Author (email) Institution	Christina Makrygianni, cmakrygianni@gmail.com (IEMC), Sophia Adam, sophia.adam@iccs.gr (ICCS)
Editor (email) Institution	Panayotis Yannakopoulos, pyannakopoulos@yahoo.co.uk (IEMC)
Leading partner	IEMC
Participating partners	ALL
Official submission date:	31/5/2020
Actual submission date:	10/06/2020

¹ **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other

² **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

Modifications Index

Date	Version
21/4/2020	0.1 First draft by Christina Makrygianni
1/5/2020	0.2 Drafted and edited by Panos Yannakopoulos
28/05/2020	0.3 Final editing by Panos Yannakopoulos
03/06/2020	0.4 Partners final refinement and Proof reading
5/06/2020	1.0 Final document

This work is a part of the HYPERION project. HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory board
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Climate Change
CH	Cultural Heritage
CoP	Communities of Practices
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
GA	Grant Agreement
GPL	General Public License
HRAP	Holistic Risk Assessment Platform
ICCS	Institute of Communications and Computer Systems
IEMC	Intercultural Euro-Mediterranean Center for UNESCO
PC	Project Coordinator
PCT	Project Coordination Team
PM	Project Manager
QM	Quality Manager
QP	Quality Plan
RG	Resilience Guard GmbH
WP	Work Package
SG	Structural/Geotechnical (tool)
PET	Privacy Enhancing Technologies

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Executive Summary

The objective of Work Package 9 is to “Create and enhance project visibility and its most important outputs to pave the way for wide-spread acceptance and implementation of the results, while respecting security/confidentiality matters with regard to sensitive project outcomes” (HYPERION DoA p.61) and achieve a high level of impact for the project and its results.

The scope of this document is to report the work performed in HYPERION for Task 9.4, entitled: “*Ongoing and special dissemination efforts*”, during M1-M12 of the project. This task focuses on regular and special dissemination activities of HYPERION outcomes, as they become available during the project. Activities under this task are explained in more detail on the following pages of this document, for all possible and appropriate channels and means.

The purpose of the info pack in deliverable 9.4 is to report and highlight consortium’s initiatives to inform, engage, create awareness and promote information about HYPERION’s assets and developments so as to achieve a high level of impact for the project and its results.

A detailed communication and dissemination plan is already developed in Deliverable 9.3 and is accessible to all consortium partners so that they can refer to it and communicate the well-defined HYPERION messages to its identified target audiences.

Moreover, this document displays communication collateral offered in the info pack and messaging designed by IEMC (WP9 leader and the leader of Tasks 9.1-9.4.)

Partners may adapt them as they see fit when communicating HYPERION in their channels.

1. INTRODUCTION

The scope of this document Deliverable D9.4 “Information packs for referenced and networked communication amplifiers” is to present the HYPERION communication elements available for consortium partners to communicate the project and support them to achieve a high-level impact for the project activities, its developments and valuable outcomes.

1.1 Intended Readership

This Deliverable is “Public”, thus accessible to anyone interested.

It is primarily written for the European Commission (EC) Project Officer (PO) and the consortium members of the HYPERION Project in order to inform them about the HYPERION brand identity and dedicated guidelines, the project’s communication and dissemination materials and channels as well as the planned activities. More specifically, it serves as an instrument that helps them understand the communication’s objectives of the project and how these could contribute to project’s awareness in an efficient and effective way.

Nevertheless, special effort and attention has been given in making this report as a stand-alone document and comprehensible for the general public.

2. Contents of the Information pack – Assets and Collateral

The sample shown here contains communication collateral (tangible things that can be held, touched and passed physically from one person to another) and digital communication.

2.1 Collateral Communication

2.1.1 HYPERION BRANDING

As already outlined in D9.1 “Corporate identity and general templates for dissemination material”, dedicated HYPERION’s visual identity and branding was created by specialists from the beginning of the project, with the aim to ensure the visual consistency and the effective graphical identity of the project and to support the dissemination and communication activities.

The provided brand identity elements (logo, fonts, colour palettes), the Brand Identity Guidelines (BIG) and the templates (for powerpoint presentations, letters, agenda, minutes, etc.) that have been produced, form a complete and effective toolkit for assisting both the HYPERION consortium and external professionals to utilize the communication and dissemination tools in a consistent, effective and efficient way.

Both BIG and templates have been presented and efficiently explained to all HYPERION partners while have been uploaded to the project’s common online collaborative tool (REDMINE) to be easily accessible by all.

2.1.2 HYPERION General Presentation

A HYPERION general presentation was created by HYPERION’s Coordinator, the ICCS, to assist all partners’ activities aiming at disseminating the project to various audiences via conferences, workshops and other events. The project presentation is a Microsoft PowerPoint slideshow with text and pictures about HYPERION, and is targeted at a broad audience. The slideshow presents the overall project, the challenges that comes across, its vision, main components and main facts. The presentation will be updated regularly, as new project results come available.

Image 1: HYPERION General Presentation

2.1.3 Leaflet

A six-fold leaflet was designed focusing on a general presentation of the project and its components and illustrating its concepts, mission, impact and test sites (see Figures 1). The leaflet will be updated each year according to the project's developments and needs.

Recent studies highlight the potential impact of Climate Change and geo-hazards (such as landslides and earthquakes) on historic areas hosting Cultural Heritage sites and monuments, which in turn yield significant adverse impacts on economies, politics and societies. The deterioration of Cultural Heritage sites is one of the biggest challenges in conservation; aspects such as building technologies/materials, structural responses, preventive measures and restoration strategies, resilience and adaptation methodologies must be considered.

fb.me/HyperionEUProject
 twitter.com/EuHyperion
 linkedin.com/company/HyperionEUProject
 www.hyperion-project.eu

Project Coordinator: Dr. Angelos Amditis
 Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), 9-Iroon Polytechniou str.
 GR-157 73 Zografou Athens, Greece
 a.amditis@ics.gr

HYPERION will leverage existing tools and services (e.g., climate/extreme events models, and their impacts, decay models of building materials, Copernicus services, etc.), novel technologies (terrestrial and satellite imaging for wide-area inspection, advanced machine learning, etc.) to deliver an integrated resilience assessment platform, addressing multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster, adapted and efficient response, and sustainable reconstruction of historic areas.

HYPERION will take into account the local eco-systems in the Cultural Heritage areas, mapping out their interactions and following a truly integrated/sustainable reconstruction approach, by incorporating active communities participation and by supporting new business models based on the concept of a "load-balancing" economy, and offering financial risk-transfer tools that can ensure the immediate funds availability to fuel timely build-back-better efforts.

THE PARTNERS

The HYPERION integrated resilience assessment platform offers an overarching strategy that includes risk management, protection and preparedness as complementary strategies to prevent damages to cultural sites, identify and ward off additional threats and promote adaptation, reconstruction and other post-disruption strategies to restore normal conditions to the historic area, as well as long-term strategic approaches to adapt to Climate Change and to wield policy tools for economic resilience.

42-month EC Funded project Start date: 1st June 2019. This work is part of the HYPERION project. The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 821054.

HYPERION's ambition is to produce a comprehensive tool to assess the threats of CC in tandem with other natural hazards, visualize the built heritage and cultural landscape under future climate scenarios, model the effects of different adaptation strategies, and ultimately prioritize any rehabilitation actions to best allocate funds in both pre- and post-event environments. In order to meet this goal, HYPERION will set out to produce the following outcomes until the end of 2022.

- Reliable quantification of climatic, hydrological and atmospheric stressors
- Analysis of building materials and deterioration processes
- Implementation of a Hygro-Thermal simulation
- Improved prediction of Structural and Geotechnical safety risk
- Environmental and material monitoring including state identification and damage diagnosis
- Design of a Holistic Resilience Assessment Platform and a Decision-Support-System, enabling communities' participation
- On-site Integration, Demonstration and Validation of the HYPERION platform through case studies in Greece, Italy, Norway and Spain
- Project Handbook
- Multi-Hazard modelling

TEST SITES

HYPERION will perform extensive tests in four demo sites, in Greece (Rhodes), Spain (Granada), Norway (Tønsberg) and Italy (Venice). The historic areas will be modelled at building level through reduced-order models based on archetype structures of each area. A number of selected structures (CH value) will be modelled and monitored in detail. The demonstration shall prove the suitability of the HYPERION platform for multiple hazard assessment and optimized operational and strategic decisions for management and maintenance of the historic areas, considering as well other hazards relevant for other sections of the city.

The City of Venice

The Municipality of Rhodes

The Municipality of Tønsberg (Norway)

The Municipality of Granada

IMPACT

- Multi-hazard risk understanding
- Better preparedness
- Faster, adapted, efficient response
- Sustainable reconstruction
- Quantitative Impact assessment

HYPERION COMPONENTS

Figure 1: HYPERION's first Leaflet

2.1.4 Poster

A HYPERION poster was also created presenting the general concept of the project (See Fig. 2). Other poster will be produced according to partner's needs during the project's runtime.

HYPERION's ambition is to produce a comprehensive tool to assess the threats of Climate Change in tandem with other natural hazards, visualize the built heritage and cultural landscape under future climate scenarios, model the effects of different adaptation strategies, and ultimately prioritize any rehabilitation actions to best allocate funds in both pre- and post-event environments.

Hyperion

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MAIN COMPONENTS	Technologies	Services	Tools
	Advanced Machine Learning Participative Cultural Heritage	Copernicus Climate Change (C3S) EURO-CORDEX Galileo Copernicus Emergency Management (CEMS)	Satellite Imaging Terrestrial Imaging Wide Area Inspection Climate/Extreme Events models Decay Models of materials

THE PARTNERS

42-month EC Funded project. Start date: 1st June 2019. This work is part of the HYPERION project. The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054.

Project Coordinator: Dr. Angelos Amditis, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), 9 Iroon Polytechniou str. GR-157 73 Zografou Athens, Greece, aamd@ics.fORTH.gr

Figure 2: HYPERION's Poster

2.1.5 Banner

A Roll up banner template has also been created displaying the project's visual identity and providing a particularly practical tool with which to promote HYPERION and deliver its assets in workshops and conferences. The banner have been also included in D9.1 and D9.3, as was ready from the beginning of the project.

Hyperion

A resilience assessment platform, addressing multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster/adapted/efficient response and sustainable reconstruction of historic areas.

Figure 3: HYPERION's Banner

The updated banner is presented in Fig. 3. The modifications that are included, were necessary after Dr. Antonis Kalis replaced Nikos Frangakis, and the county of “Vestfold” changed its logo, the coat of arms and its name after the unification of the two former counties of Telemark and Vestfold (since the 1st of January 2020 renamed as “Vestfold and Telemark”).

2.1.6 Videos

The first video of the project is currently under development presenting the challenges HYPERION's faces, its vision and objectives. It will be released to all social media and the website by June 2020.

2.2 Digital Communication

2.2.1 Website

At month 5 a website, address: <https://www.hyperion-project.eu/> was designed and is continuously updated since, with all the HYPERION latest news, events and publications. It was launched in its final version in month eight. The HYPERION website has become an important factor for the HYPERION dissemination and communication plan. The structure (sitemap) of the website is designed to provide visitors immediate access to all public information of the project. For the visitors' convenience, almost all, subpages of the website are accessible by the main page with respective quick links. Moreover, links to the social media accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook), amplifying the branding of the project, are available on the <https://www.hyperion-project.eu/> of the website. The "Home" page of the website is presented in Figure 4 while the sitemap structure of the website is presented in Figure 5. Website statistics up to M12 of the project are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7 below.

Figure 7 illustrates the progress on the number of unique visitors for the last three months. The latter images show the users' behaviour while visiting the site for the same period.

Figure 4: Program Website (home page)

HYPERION's website is divided in eight menus, as listed below:

1. About
2. Partners
3. Test Sites
4. Results to date
5. Newsletter
6. Get Involved
7. Liaisons

8. Contact us

Figure 5: Website sitemap structure

Website accessing information

The Home Page was visited 1281 times. The Total Clicks, in every page, were 4431.

The Newsletter Subscribers are 16. The number of unique visitors per country is presented in Figure 6 (for the top ten) the total number being 378. It is worth to mention the project's visibility and dissemination to non-project member countries, i.e. the United States, the United Kingdom, France and the Netherlands. The last thirty days, May, the number of unique visitors is 262 and 61% of them are new users.

1.	Greece	168
2.	Italy	86
3.	United States	33
4.	Norway	28
5.	Cyprus	15
6.	Germany	13
7.	United Kingdom	13
8.	Spain	8
9.	France	7
10.	Netherlands	7

Figure 6: Top 10 countries from which the HYPERION's Website was accessed

Overview Report

Last 30 days: April 27 - May 26, 2020

Figure 7: Website 30-day overview report

Future Activities

The HYPERION website will be constantly updated with new content (news, participation in events, workshops, publications e.tc.) in order to keep the visitors informed on the latest advances of the project. Feedback from the visitors is also considered. The content and structure of the HYPERION website can be updated in the future to become more user friendly with useful information that would allow target groups to quickly understand what the project is about and what it has to offer. IEMC is constantly working and updating the content and the structure of the website.

2.2.2 HYPERION in Partners' organisations websites

In order to increase the visibility of the project and as a sign of the involvement of the consortium partners in project's communication activities, detailed information about HYPERION's assets is published on partners' organisations dedicated websites as well as in EC's portals.

Table 1: Partners' websites and the HYPERION partners' URL

No	Partner	Website
1	Institute of Communications and Computer Systems	https://i-sense.iccs.gr/
2	Ilmatieteen Laitos/ Finnish Meteorological Institute	https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/ https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/projects-of-the-atmospheric-dispersion-modelling-group
3	Resilience Guard GmbH	https://www.resilienceguard.ch/ https://www.resilienceguard.ch/company/eu-horizon-2020/
4	Oslomet - Storbyuniversitetet/ Oslo Metropolitan University	https://www.oslomet.no https://www.oslomet.no/en/research/research-groups/sustainabuilt https://www.oslomet.no/en/research/projects/horizon-2020 https://uni.oslomet.no/serq/projects/
5	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) School of Civil engineering and School of Rural and Surveying Engineering	http://www.ntua.gr http://users.ntua.gr/divamva/projects.html
6	RisaSicherheitsanalysen GmbH GmbH	http://www.risa.eu/ http://www.risa.eu/de/safetyanalyses/contractresearch.php
7	Universita Degli Studi Di Padova / University of Padova Department of Geoscience	https://www.geoscienze.unipd.it/ https://www.geoscienze.unipd.it/hyperion-project
8	Universidad De Granada/University of Granada	https://www.ugr.es/en/
9	Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis/ Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	https://www.auth.gr/
10	Cy.R.I.C – Cyprus Research and Innovation Center Ltd	https://www.cyric.eu/ https://www.cyric.eu/project/hyperion/
11	Universita Iuav Di Venezia/ Laboratory for the Analysis of	http://www.iuav.it/lama

	Ancient Materials (LAMA)	
12	Vestfold Fylkeskommune/ Vestfold and Telemark County	https://www.vtfk.no/
13	Comune di Venezia (City of Venice)	https://www.comune.venezia.it/it/content/hyperion
14	Dimos Rodou (Municipality of Rhodes)	https://www.rhodes.gr/
15	Ephorate of Antiquities of the Dodecanese	https://www.culture.gov.gr/en/ministry/SitePages/vi-ewyphresia.aspx?iID=1705
16	Ayuntamiento De Granada	https://www.granada.org/
17	Intercultural Euro-Mediterranean Center for UNESCO	https://www.iemcunesco.org/ https://www.iemcunesco.org/activities
18	RED SpA	https://www.redrisk.com/ https://www.redrisk.com/redeng/Projects/layoutprogetto.php?project=project17

HYPERION in Project Coordinator's (ICCS) Website

The screenshot shows the SENSE GROUP website. The main navigation menu includes: Home, Research Areas, **Projects**, Members, Publications, News, Video Gallery, Dictionary, Work with us, and Contact. A search bar is located in the top right corner.

The breadcrumb trail reads: You are here: Home / Projects / Ongoing Projects / HYPERION.

HYPERION

Development of a Decision Support System for Improved Resilience and Sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas to cope with Climate Change and Extreme Events based on Novel Sensors and Advanced Modelling Tools: The HYPERION Approach

HYPERION aims to leverage

- existing tools and services (e.g., climate/extreme events models, and their impacts, decay models of building materials, Copernicus services, etc.) and
- novel technologies (terrestrial and satellite imaging for wide-area inspection, advanced machine learning, etc.)

to deliver an integrated resilience assessment platform, addressing multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster, adapted and efficient response, and sustainable reconstruction of historic areas.

HYPERION will take into account the local eco-systems in the CH areas, mapping out their interactions and following a truly integrated/sustainable reconstruction approach (technical, social, institutional, environmental and economic level), by incorporating active communities participation (using the PLUGGY social platform) and by supporting new business models based on the concept of a "load-balancing" economy, (using an algorithm that acts like a "reverse proxy", distributing client traffic across different companies within the same sector) and offering financial risk-transfer tools (insurance, Catastrophe-CAT-bonds) that can ensure the immediate funds availability to fuel timely build-back-better efforts.

Website: www.hyperion-project.eu
 Facebook: [Hyperion EU Project](#)
 Twitter: [@EUHyperion](#)

Figure 8: ICCS website promoting the HYPERION project

HYPERION in Industrial partners' organisations websites

- 1) Cyprus Research and Innovation Center Ltd (CYRIC). The page which promotes HYPERION is presented in figure 9 that follows.

Figure 9: CyRIC's webpage with the project's acknowledgement

- 2) Resilience Guard GmbH (RG). The webpage mentioning HYPERION, is posted on the website, since December 2019 on the following address:

<https://www.resilienceguard.ch/company/eu-horizon-2020/>. The following figure 10 presents the first page.

Figure 10: Resilience Guard (RG) Webpage promoting HYPERION

- 3) Red Risk engineering Development SpA (RED). A screenshot from RED is shown in Figure 11 that follows.

Figure 11: Screenshot from RED's relevant webpage

- 4) RisaSicherheitsanalysen GmbH (RISA). The HYPERION project is presented in both languages (English and German for the broader dissemination of the project). The screenshot from its page in English is presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Screenshot from RISA's Webpage

HYPERION in Research/Academic partners' organisations websites

A sample from the participating Institutes and Universities webpages and the related articles presenting the HYPERION project is shown in the following figures.

1. IUAV University of Venice, Laboratory for the Analysis of Ancient Materials (IUAV)

The screenshot shows the IUAV website header with the logo and the text 'Università Iuav di Venezia LA RICERCA'. Below the header is a navigation menu with categories: LA RICERCA IN IUAV, RISULTATI, LABORATORI, BANDI, and SERVIZI. The main content area is titled 'temi di ricerca' and lists various research topics. The 'spun off' section highlights the HYPERION project, providing details on its objectives, scientific responsible, sector, duration, budget, and funding.

LA RICERCA IN IUAV	RISULTATI	LABORATORI	BANDI	SERVIZI
temi di ricerca				
progetti di ricerca				
attori aggregazioni				
strutture	Horizon 2020			
reti partners	HYPERION			
spin off	Development of a Decision Support System for Improved Resilience & Sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas to cope with Climate Change & Extreme Events based on Novel Sensors and Modelling Tools responsabile scientifico Fabrizio Antonelli settore GEO/09 durata 42 mesi dal 01/06/2019 al 30/11/2022 budget progetto Euro 5.997.728,75 budget Iuav Euro 260.445,00 finanziamento Iuav Euro 260.445,00			

[scheda progetto >>](#)

Figure 13: Screenshot from the Webpage of IUAV

2. The web page inside the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) pages: <https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/projects-of-the-atmospheric-dispersion-modelling-group>.

The screenshot shows the FMI website page for atmospheric dispersion modelling projects. The page lists various projects, including CAMS 50, CAMS 81, CAMS 95, and several EU-funded projects. The HYPERION project is highlighted in a red box at the bottom of the list.

- EU/AIRCOAT (2018-2021). Air Induced friction Reducing ship COATING. Horizon 2020 framework project. [Project description](#) .
- EU/beAWARE (2017-2019). Enhancing decision support and management services in extreme weather climate events. [Project website](#) .
- EU/EnviSum/BSR-Interreg (2016-2019). Environmental impact of low emissions shipping: measurements and modelling strategies. [Project description](#) . [Project website](#) .
- EU/EUNADICS-AV (2016-2019). European Natural Airborne Disaster Information and Coordination System for Aviation. [Project website](#) .
- EU/ERA4CS URban CLIMate services URCLIM (2017-2020). [Project description](#) .
- EU/ERA4CS Integrated services and approaches for assessing effects of climate change and extreme events for fire risk prevention SERV_FORFIRE (2017-2020). [Project description](#) .
- EU/BlueSky (2017-2019). A commercial platform providing operational Air Quality services using EO data. [Information in CORDIS data base](#) .
- EU/EOPEN (2017-2020). opEn InterOperable Platform for unified access and analysis of Earth observationN data. [Project information](#) . [Information in CORDIS data base](#) .
- EU/EXHAUSTION (2019-2023). Shipping contributions to inland pollution push for the enforcement of regulations. [Information in CORDIS data base](#) .
- EU/HOPE (2018-2021) Healthy Outdoor Premises for Everyone. [HOPE project page on the EU Urban Innovative Actions site](#) . [Project web site](#) .
- EU/HYPERION (2019-2022). Exposure to heat and air pollution in Europe – cardiopulmonary impacts and benefits of mitigation and adaptation. [Information in CORDIS data base](#) .

Figure 14: Screenshot from the Webpage of FMI

3. OSLO Metropolitan University (OSLOMET)

OSLOMET participates with two research groups: The research group from the Faculty of Technology Art and Design and the Structural Engineering Research Group. The following figure 15 present the HYPERION project of the above mentioned groups.

https://www.oslomet.no/en/research/research-groups/sustainabuilt

Sustainable Built Environment (SustainaBUILT)
This research group belongs to the Faculty of Technology, Art and Design. We research sustainable engineering solutions for the built environment.

with energy storage.

Head of Research Group

Peter Schild
Professor
+47 67 23 86 41 | +47 415 11 285 | Peter.Schild@oslomet.no

Members

More about the Research

Projects

- **Hyperion** (hyperion-project.eu). Resilience and sustainable reconstruction of historic areas to cope with climate change and hazard events.
- **BestVent** (sintef.no). Best demand-controlled Ventilation strategies to maximise air quality in occupied spaces and minimise energy use in empty spaces. Postdoctoral position and master-thesis in collaboration with SINTEF Community.
- **SvalVent**. Cool and comfortable demand-controlled ventilation, with individual control, for low-energy cooling of office buildings

https://uni.oslomet.no/serg/projects/

Structural Engineering Research Group
Web site of SERG at OsloMet

Home People Projects Research Publications

Projects

HYPERION Project

Full title: Development of a Decision Support System for Improved Resilience & Sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas to cope with Climate Change & Extreme Events based on Novel Sensors and Modelling Tools
Project number: 821054
Financing: Horizon 2020 (EU)

Figure 15: Screenshots from the Webpages of OSLOMET

4. University of Padova (UNIPD)

Figure 16: Screenshots from the Webpages of UNIPD

HYPERION Project is mentioned on the website of the Department of Geosciences (University of Padova - UNIPD) (<https://www.geoscienze.unipd.it/>). A slot on the banner of the Department contains a picture and the Project title, which is linked to a page containing a presentation of the Project, and links to the Project website and the social media. A QR code link to the Project homepage is also included, to encourage access via mobile phone (<https://www.geoscienze.unipd.it/hyperion-project>).

In addition, direct link to the HYPERION site is available in the e-mail signature of participants.

5. University of Granada (UGR)

The Engineering and Infrastructure Group from the University of Granada (UGR) is involved on Hyperion with Prof Hernández-Montes as PI. The dissemination of the project is carried out through the group's website (<https://wpd.ugr.es/~tep190/wordpress/>). A screenshot of the website is shown below.

Figure 17: Screenshot from the Webpage of UGR

Specifically, a new section named *HYPERION project* has been included. In this section, a brief description of the project is provided, including consortium composition. In addition, a direct link to the HYPERION website is provided as well as the HYPERION poster. Finally, some pictures of the two Cultural Heritage buildings investigated by the group are provided.

HYPERION in End Users' organisations websites

A sample of the participating end users (authorities) is presented in the following figures:

1. Municipality of Rhodes (DR)

ΑΝΑΡΤΗΣΗ	ΟΔΗΓΟΣ	ΠΡΟΚΗΡΥΞΗ	ΕΚΔΗΛΩΣΗ
23	ΓΥΜΝΑΣΙΟΥ-ΛΥΚΕΙΟΥ ΚΑΙ ΕΠΑ.Λ. ΑΡΧΑΓΓΕΛΟΥ ΔΗΜΟΥ ΡΟΔΟΥ	1.250.000,00	2018
24	ΑΝΑΔΕΙΞΗ ΡΕΜΑΤΙΑΣ ΨΙΝΘΟΥ	327.000,00	3700/31-10-2018
25	VISITS4U	13.281,00	1/7/2016
26	IN-PREP	316.500,00	1/9/2017
27	HYPERION	140.750,00	1/6/2019
28	Ψηφιακή πλατφόρμα καταγραφής πολιττικών εκδηλώσεων και έξυπνη εφαρμογή οδηγού πολιτισμού για τη Ρόδο	100.000,00	491/03-05-2019
29	Ανάπλαση και κυκλοφοριακές ρυθμίσεις από το Λιμάνι Ακαντιάς ως τη Νέα Μαρίνα Ρόδου	3.038.400,00	1535/12-06-2019
	LIFE-IP AdaptInGR - Boosting the		GRANT AGREEMENT

Figure 18: Screenshot from the Webpage of DR

2. City of Venice (CVI)

Hyperion
 Sviluppo di un sistema di supporto decisionale per migliorare la resilienza e la ricostruzione sostenibile delle aree storiche per far fronte ai cambiamenti climatici e agli eventi estremi basato su sensori e strumenti di modellazione innovativi.

<https://www.hyperion-project.eu>
<https://www.facebook.com/HyperionEUProject/>
<https://www.linkedin.com/company/hyperioneuproject/>
<https://twitter.com/EuHyperion>

Programma europeo: HORIZON 2020

Figure 19: Screenshot from the Webpage of CIV

HYPERION in European Commission's Portal

The screenshot shows the CORDIS website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'HOME', 'RESULTS PACKS', 'RESEARCH/EU MAGAZINES', 'NEWS & EVENTS', 'PROJECTS & RESULTS', and 'ABOUT US'. A search bar is also present. The main content area features a 'Fact Sheet' for the project 'Development of a Decision Support System for Improved Resilience & Sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas to cope with Climate Change & Extreme Events based on Novel Sensors and Modelling Tools'. The 'Objective' section describes the project's goals, including the development of a research framework for downscaling climate and atmospheric composition, and the use of novel sensors and modelling tools. The 'Project information' sidebar provides details such as the grant agreement ID (821054), start date (1 June 2019), end date (30 November 2022), and funding sources (H2020-EU.3.5.6, H2020-EU.3.5.1.2). A donut chart shows the overall budget (€ 5 997 728,75) and the EU contribution (€ 5 997 728,75). The project is coordinated by the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems.

Figure 20: Project's presentation at CORDIS website

The following figure 21 presents the media and the partners through whom the perspective followers are accessing the HYPERION website. The most popular is Facebook and after it twitter followed by Research Gate.

1.	m.facebook.com	38
2.	t.co	27
3.	researchgate.net	21
4.	l.facebook.com	18
5.	linkedin.com	17
6.	facebook.com	15
7.	geoscienze.unipd.it	14
8.	comune.venezia.it	10
9.	iemcunesco.org	10
10.	oslomet.no	10

Figure 21: Project's website reference point

The HYPERION webpages visited by the audience are listed in order, from the higher to lower accessibility. To accessibility directs us towards the enhancement of the information to the mostly visited sections. Also we aim to increase the accessibility of the other sections of our website. (The numbers indicate their sequence in the website map)

- Home page (1)
- Partners (1.2)
- Test Sites (1.3)
- Hyperion's vision (1.1.1)
- News (1.5.1)
- Get Involved (1.6)
- Publications (1.4.3)
- Newsletter (1.5.2)
- Deliverables (1.4.1)
- Stakeholders (1.1.4)

2.2.3 Social Media

In recent years, social media has become ubiquitous and instrumental for communication, networking and content sharing purposes. Successful social media activities will help HYPERION to increase its visibility and maximise its potential outreach. Therefore, HYPERION project actively engages in social media as a channel for communication of the project idea and outcomes as well as for interaction with target audiences. In month 6, HYPERION accounts in three social networks, LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook, were set up and activated. Recently Research Gate and Instagram were also launched and the information was disseminated to the partners. Instagram's Ad Platform has access to the most advanced social media can build an audience that Will stay connected with our project and lastly one of the main benefits of Instagram that separates it from all other social media platforms, is that it's photo-centric.

2.2.3.1 LINKEDIN

For HYPERION project, LinkedIn is used as an effective tool for collaboration, sharing best practices, and targeted marketing efforts. Up to the time of creating this document, the HYPERION LinkedIn account had 280 connections and the HYPERION LinkedIn page had 39 followers.

Figure 22: Project LinkedIn statistics: Access via mobile or desktop

2.2.3.2 TWITTER

The HYPERION (HyperionEUproject) Twitter account (@EuHyperion) was established in May 2019, to engage our project on a social media platform (<https://twitter.com/EuHyperion>). We have already started to tweet about the project's aim, the consortium and related topics of interest. IECM, with support from other partners tweet regularly throughout the project lifetime, about news, results, job opportunities and other topics relevant for our project in order to support the impact of our website.

Figure 23: Sample tweet from the project Leader

Figure 24: Twitter main page (end of April and end of May)

The content strategy that was setup for twitter was: tweets that included links to web content (blog posts, website pages, PDF documents, as well as a photos and videos).

Up to the time of the creation of this document, the Twitter account had 190 followers. 100 tweets were published until May 28th.

Among our followers the most important are: English Heritage (179,5K followers), Ilmatieteen laitos (168,1K followers), World Meteorological Organization (88,7K followers), Europanosträ (13,2K followers), UNESCOEU (6,488 followers), ClimateHeritage (2,683 followers), and PLUGGY (454 followers).

Figure 25: Twitter analytics during May and April 2020

Figure 26: Tweet Activity analytics – reaction to posts

Figure 27: Tweet analytics for the top tweet and the top mentioned reference

2.2.3.3 FACEBOOK

Facebook is the world’s largest social network, and one which enables heretofore unheard-of avenues of communication. The content strategy that was setup for this network unfolds like this: posts that educate while entertaining, informational videos, and anything that generates hype, and therefore comments and shares. For HYPERION

project, a Facebook page has been set up and up to the time of creating this document, it had 321 followers. Our Facebook page was liked by 304 followers.

Figure 28: HYPERION Facebook Account main page

Figure 29: HYPERION Facebook account statistics

2.2.3.4 RESEARCH GATE

Research Gate is a European commercial social networking site for scientists and researchers to share papers, ask and answer questions, and find collaborators. We are using this site and currently our account has 20 followers and 216 reads. We aim to upload

all the presentations and journal papers to it and maximize the scientific impact of the HYPERION project.

Figure 30: Research Gate statistics

2.2.3.5 INSTAGRAM

Lastly, as our world become more digital and “visual” after the pandemia, we also decided to explore the benefits of using Instagram. The main reason is, its wide spread among people and its interconnection with the most social media.

2.3 KPIs in HYPERION Social Media channels

Several KPIs have been established for WP9, which can be found in D9.3, and in addition to these indicators IEMC monitors throughout the project the impact and engagement of each publication.

The statistics of the social media channel of HYPERION per publication up to M12 of the project is depicted in the Table 2 below.

Table 2: Statistics of the social media channels of HYPERION

| LinkedIn page
 |
|--|--|--------|-----------------|--|
| Connections | Followers | Tweets | Engagement rate | Engaged Users ³ |
| 41 | 190 | 102 | 2.3% | 310/306 |

2.3.1 Additional partners' posts for Social Media and links

In general the different social media platforms of Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook follow a similar strategy.

Add to the conversation by

- Supporting other projects or organisations with a reply or re-post,
- Uploading news on relevant events of other organisations and HYPERION project,
- Creating new content within the HYPERION project through blogs or project news items.

a) Screenshots from the Facebook accounts:

Vestfold and Telemark county (VFK), upload all activities performed on their Facebook account: <https://www.facebook.com/KulturarvVestfoldTelemark> (See Fig. 31)

Also, Università Iuav Di Venezia/Laboratory for the Analysis of Ancient Materials (LAMA), (IUAV), launched two different Facebook sites (one is the department and one the University) for the program needs. The LAMA-LabCoMaC laboratory has a personal Facebook page, approved by the IUAV authority, in which, periodically, information about the Hyperion project is shared with the followers. Link: [@LAMALabCoMaCluav](https://www.facebook.com/LAMALabCoMaCluav) (Fig. 33)

The project developments are also reported on the official IUAV Facebook page dedicated to the research. Link: [@ricercaiuav](https://www.facebook.com/ricercaiuav) (Fig. 33).

³ The number of unique people who engaged in certain ways with Facebook Page posts, for example by commenting on, liking, sharing, or clicking upon particular elements of the post.

Figure 31: Vestfold and Telemark county HYPERION activities on Facebook

Figure 32: Posts from ICCS I-SENSE Group Facebook Account

Figure 33: Facebook sample posts from IUAV

b) Screenshots from the Twitter accounts

Figure 34: Tweets from ICCS I-SENSE Group Twitter Account

c) Partners' LinkedIn Sample Posts

As for the dissemination actions, Resilience Guard GmbH posted twice on LinkedIn about the project. Also, HYPERION's Coordinator, the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), posted on its LinkedIn account (Figure 35).

Figure 35: Sample posts from ICCS I-SENSE LinkedIn Account

Table 3: Twitter Accounts

1	ICCS	https://twitter.com/lccsNtua
2	FMI	https://twitter.com/meteorologist
3	RG	https://twitter.com/ResilienceGuard
4	OSLOMET	https://twitter.com/OsloMet
5	CYRIC	https://twitter.com/Cy_RIC
6	IEMC	https://twitter.com/euro_unesco

Table 4: Facebook Accounts

1	ICCS	https://www.facebook.com/search/top/?q=%CE%95%CE%A0%CE%99%CE%A3%CE%95%CE%A5
2	RG	https://www.facebook.com/ResilienceGuard
3	CYRIC	https://www.facebook.com/cyric.eu
4	IUAV	@ricercaiuav and @LAMALabCoMaCluav
5	VFK	https://www.facebook.com/KulturarvVestfoldTelemark/
6	CVI	https://www.facebook.com/Comunedivenezia
7	DR	https://www.facebook.com/DimosRodouOfficial

8	ADG	https://www.facebook.com/AyuntamientodeGranada
9	IEMC	https://www.facebook.com/Intercultural-Euromediterranean-Centre-for-Unesco-199797093372547

Content: Latest news in the field of improved Resilience and Sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas to cope with Climate Change and Extreme Events and related disciplines of HYPERION partners.

Function: Find latest news on the interdisciplinary fields within HYPERION project and connect with other groups to build an audience for the HYPERION project and HYPERION initiatives.

URL link:

<https://twitter.com/EuHyperion>

<https://www.facebook.com/HyperionEUProject/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/hyperioneuproject/?viewAsMember=true>

<https://www.researchgate.net/project/HYPERION-2>

3. Dissemination Means & Communication Amplifiers

By identifying the major target groups and the means/ways of communication in the project, this section will present the different impacts generated up to date.

3.1 Scientific Publications

Publications in scientific journals with topics relevant to the research and innovation work will target the scientific communities directly or indirectly in the scope of HYPERION. These activities reinforce the project awareness, allow HYPERION concepts and solutions to leverage other research projects, foster cross-project cooperation and provide fundamental means of peer reviewing of the scientific approaches of HYPERION.

The following articles have been published to date:

Table 5: List of Journal publications

Title	Partner	Journal	Authors
Performance analysis of open source time series InSAR methods for deformation monitoring over a broader mining region	NTUA	Remote Sensing Journal	<i>Karathanassi Vassilia and Kleanthis Karamvasis</i>
Fine-tuning Self-Organizing Maps for Sentinel-2 imagery: Separating Clouds from Bright Surfaces	NTUA	Remote Sensing Journal	<i>Viktoria Kristollari and Vassilia Karathanassi</i>

Table 6: List of papers under review

Title	Partner	Journal	Authors
Structural Vulnerability Assessment of Heritage Timber Buildings: A Literature Review	OSLOMET	Engineering Structures journal	<i>Amirhosein Shabani, Mahdi Kioumars, Vagelis Plevris, Haris Stamatopoulos</i>
Model type effects on the estimated seismic response of a 20-story steel moment resisting frame	NTUA	ASCE Journal of Structural Engineering	<i>Lachanas, C.G. Vamvatsikos D.</i>
Probabilistic identification of surface recession patterns in heritage buildings based on digital photogrammetry	UGR	Construction and Building Materials	<i>María L. Jalón, Juan Chiachío, Luisa M. Gil, Enrique Hernández</i>

Table 7: List of accepted conference papers

Title	Partner	Conference /Location	Authors
"Decision support, resilience and sustainable reconstruction of historical city cores under seismic threat: The HYPERION approach" http://www.iiees.ac.ir/fa/see8pub/ (p.546)	ICCS	8th International Conference on Seismology & Earthquake Engineering, Tehran, Iran, 11-13 Nov 2019	<i>D. Vamvatsikos & P. Bazzurro</i>
HYPERION:A decision Support System for Improved Resilience and sustainable Reconstruction of historic areas https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sxBWeIDxgGQ (3:20:41 – 3:30:30)	ICCS	Adapt Northern Heritage Conference Edinburgh, 5-6 May 2020	<i>Antonis Kalis et al.</i>
Hygrothermal performance of an old building with log walls from the region of Vestfold in Norway https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C_MkQ_iBnk (36:20- 48:24)	OSLOMET	Adapt Northern Heritage Conference Edinburgh, 5-6 May 2020	<i>P. Choidis and D. Kraniotis</i>
Hygrothermal performance of log walls in a building of 18th century and prediction of climate change impact on biological deterioration (new dates due to Covid-19)	OLSOMET, AUTH	NSB 2020 Conference (12th Nordic Symposium on Building Physics); Tallinn, Estonia, 7 – 9 Sept 2020	<i>Petros Choidis, Katerina Tsikaloudaki, and Dimitrios Kraniotis</i>
Preliminary Structural Survey of heritage timber Log houses in TØNSBERG	OSLOMET	12th international conference of structural analysis of historical construction (SAHC 2020) Barcelona, Spain, 16-18 Sept 2020	<i>Amirhosein Shabani, Haidar Hosamo, Mahdi Kioumars and Vagelis Plevris</i>
Seismic risk assessment of the ancient Temple of Aphaia in Greece (postponed due to Covid-19)	NTUA	Sendai, Japan, Sept. 2021, http://www.17wcee.jp/	<i>Melissianos V., Vamvatsikos D.</i>

Table 8: List of submitted conference papers

Title	Partner	Conference /Location	Authors
Simplified estimation of design fault displacement for buried pipelines at fault crossings	NTUA	EURODYN 2020 conference	<i>Melissianos V., Vamvatsikos D.</i>

3.2 Participation in conferences, seminars, workshops

Until M12 HYPERION project has been disseminated via the participation of consortium partners to the following events (conferences):

HYPERION in the International Conference on Seismology and Earthquake Engineering (SEE) in Tehran, Iran, 11-13 Nov 2019.

SEE, under the auspices of International Institute of Earthquake Engineering and Seismology (IIEES) organized in Iran, with the theme of “Science-based Sustainable development in Earthquake prone countries” the eighth conference that provides a unique opportunity for Academia, professionals, experts, local governments, private sector and social science practitioners to exchange and share the latest advances in earthquake risk management, building and geotechnical Science, and policy initiatives that improve resiliency. The conference is organised every 4 years. Prof. Vamvatsikos presented HYPERION’s the paper: *“Decision support, resilience and sustainable reconstruction of historical city cores under seismic threat: The HYPERION approach”*.

HYPERION in “Virtual” Adapt Northern Heritage Conference, May 5-6, 2020.

“HYPERION’s decision support system for improved resilience and sustainable reconstruction of historic areas” was presented by Dr. Antonis Kalis, Project Manager, ICCS in Session 9/Topic: Urban Assessment.

Moreover, Petros Choidis, OSLOMET, presented the research conducted at OSLOMET in the context of HYPERION regarding the *“Hygrothermal performance of an old building with log walls from the region of Vestfold in Norway”*, in Session 4/Topic: Buildings Retrofit and Fabric Assessments.

The conference explored impacts of climate change on historic places and how adaptation measures can help protect these places or manage their loss. Special themes of the conference were the cultural heritage in Arctic regions and of northern indigenous communities. The conference offered fruitful themed sessions, with blindly peer-reviewed, scholarly papers given by expert speakers involved in cultural heritage management in both research and practice. In view of the growing coronavirus outbreak in Europe, this virtual conference replaced the real-world conference, which was about to be held on the same dates in Edinburgh, Scotland.

3.3 Other impactful activities

In the first 12 months of the project, HYPERION's main assets, vision and key concepts were disseminated to project's key audiences via various means such as printed and electronic media, University lectures, and visits by authorised staff.

Media Relations, Press Releases and Media Coverage

Media relations is an important aspect of HYPERION's dissemination.

An introductory press release was written, translated and regionally adapted in partners' local languages and distributed in key journalists and bloggers specialised in culture, technology and science at the beginning of the project. HYPERION's introductory press release generated valuable publicity and some very positive news coverage in high-impact news websites, subject portals and blogs.

As the project progresses and results are generated, a number of press releases will be issued around key developments. The target media for the project is broad, spans across Europe and includes the following outlets:

- ✓ National print and broadcast
- ✓ Culture media
- ✓ Scientific media
- ✓ Online media
- ✓ European Parliament and Commission Publications

HYPERION was featured in the following key subject and news portals.

www.Archaiologia.gr, www.Archaeology & Arts.gr, www.Epixeiro.gr,
www.Popaganda.gr, www.Eirinika.gr, www.Newslink.gr, www.MadeinGreece.gr, www.ICTplus.gr

The EN press release is available on the following link: <https://www.hyperion-project.eu/in-the-media/>.

Interviews

Interview of HYPERION's Coordinator, Dr. Angelos Amditis, ICCS, and Senior Researcher, Nikos Frangakis, ICCS, in Greek high-impact newspaper "Kathimerini" about HYPERION's innovative tools and PLUGGY social platform and their valuable impact for the protection and safeguarding of European cultural heritage.

University Lectures

Dr. Angelos Amditis, HYPERION's Coordinator, presented and discussed our project's key concepts & significant contribution to the preservation and sustainable reconstruction of tangible cultural wealth for future generations with students from the School of History and Archaeology of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) in a dedicated online lecture.

MEETING with Advisory Committee Members

THE UGR group contacted Hispania Nostra which is a member of HYPERION advisory committee, (<https://www.hispanianostra.org/>).

Networking

VFK presented HYPERION project to regional politicians elected for the period 2016-2019. Main committee for culture, public health, dental health and sports. Tønsberg, 16.09.2019.

Moreover, VFK presented HYPERION to regional politicians elected for the period 2020-2024. Main committee for culture, public health, dental health and sports. Skien, 06.02.2020.

Visit to quarry - PROVISION OF SANDSTONE AND LARDIOS LITHOS SAMPLES

On 12th December 2019, staff from the Ephorate of Antiquities of the Dodecanese, which operates under the Greek Ministry of Culture and Sports, visited the modern quarry at Stegna, at Lardos area, Rhodes, to select the appropriate sandstone samples and samples from lartios stone. The samples were sent to University of Padova (UNIPD) to study the behaviour of the stone under rapid aging techniques. They had the opportunity to communicate with the local authorities the HYPERION's vision and mission and to disseminate the program activities in Rhodes.

Figure 36: Visit to Lardos and Archangelos area

4. Outline Communications programme

Each activity, demonstration exercise, forum, conference, presentation, attendance at an outreach event, meeting, publication and direct email provides an opportunity to communicate HYPERION assets.

4.1 Branding fundamentals

Our project vision is to leverage existing tools and services, novel technologies to deliver an integrated resilience assessment platform, addressing multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster, adapted and efficient response, and sustainable reconstruction of historic areas.

HYPERION Technologies, Services and Tools in Figure 37 underpins the communications programme.

Technologies	Services	Tools
Advanced Machine Learning Participative Cultural Heritage	Copernicus Climate Change (C3S) EURO-CORDEX Galileo Copernicus Emergency Management (CEMS)	Satellite Imaging Terrestrial Imaging Wide Area Inspection Climate/Extreme Events models Decay Models of materials

Figure 37: HYPERION Technologies, Tools and services

Branding fundamentals

Multi Hazard risk Understanding

Faster, Adapted, efficient response

Better preparedness,

In the framework of Communication and Dissemination all HYPERION activities lead to the general vision of the best prepared correspondents & Stakeholders. Below the Figure 38 shows the formation of the later general vision through HYPERION activities.

Figure 38: HYPERION activities lead to the general vision of the best prepared correspondents & Stakeholders

4.2 Key Performance Indicators

As already been properly considered in D9.3 Dissemination and Communication Plan, the effectiveness of HYPERION’s communication and dissemination activities is periodically measured and evaluated through monitoring of the progress against KPIs set out in the project’s DoA. In this section we provide the current status for each of the proposed KPIs.

The KPI referring to the number of members per account refers to the 42 month period. So, the division gives as result 57 members/account for year 1.

The publications in scientific ISI journals commence in month 18, and the conference presentations after month 12. The number in the following table is set to zero as none of the above was foreseen earlier than month 12.

The website visits is set to 10,000/y. As our public website was launched in February 2020 for a four month period it corresponds to 3,334 visits.

Next goal, is in close collaboration with the EC personnel, to disseminate the project vision and main results through various means offered by the EU, e.g., Horizon Magazine, research*EU results magazine, EuroNews TV etc.

Table 9: Impact evaluation through KPIs

Dissemination tools	Parameter	KPIs	May 2020 (M12)
Corporate ID & templates	Set of	1	1
Web visits	Number of visits/year (combined)	10,000	4,431 (4 months)
Social media	posts/year	minimum 150	160
	Facebook members *	57	306
	Twitter Number of followers *	57	190
	LinkedIn Number of connections*	57	41
	Research Gate members**	57	20
Established relation w/EU projects		1	3
Leaflets	Number of leaflets	1	1
Poster	Poster template	1	1
Animation Video	Number of videos	1	1
Newsletter	Issues	1	0
Conference Presentations	Number of presentations	0	3
Peer-reviewed publications	Publications in scientific ISI journals	0	2
EU dissemination networks & Mass Media	press releases per year	2	2
	media articles in popular media	1	1
	interview on Radio and/or TV; Participation in prioritised EU events	1	1
Annual Magazine	Issues per year	1	0

- *Corresponds to the annual number.
- ** the account was launched in April 2020.

The Annual magazine will be distributed to the program members on the 20th of June. Also it will be launched to the public via the Website and the social media. All the activities performed to date, are included in this first issue.

In parallel, a month later, the newsletter will appear to the website, and all social media to inform the stakeholders and the people who are registered about the activities to follow in the next six months.

5. Conclusion

HYPERION project has conducted various dissemination & communication activities for the first 12 months.

The accomplishments could be summarized as follows:

HYPERION website final version was launched and is regularly being updated

HYPERION project's social media are now available to spread project's results

HYPERION's first leaflet was created and was distributed to all participants

The HYPERION poster was launched in the beginning of month 12, and was distributed to all partners

HYPERION team members participated in several scientific conferences

The results from the first studies, carried out in Norway and in Greece, were published in three (3) scientific journals (namely: Engineering Structures (1) and remote Sensing (2))

The project was advertised in printed media and promoted to local authorities and politicians by the participants who are on the vicinity.

High multiplier factor will also be the lecturing of Dr. Amditis, an initiative that targets the creation of elective courses related to the scope of HYPERION and delivered to the students.

The project will continue to intensify its activities during the following months, as more scientific results will be available. They will be disseminated, increasing usable channels and number of people reached (stakeholders, researchers, public etc.).

APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1

1. HYPERION EU PROJECT Website Sitemap

APPENDIX 2

2. VIDEO'S SCENARIO (Suggested script by ICCS)

HYPERION -1st Short Animated Video

1st Part **Suggested Title: Challenges** Storyline (for both narration & subtitles):

Environmental threats—both natural and human-made—have long threatened cultural sites.

Monuments and sites that have stood on the Earth for centuries, enduring heritage symbols, have always suffered from exposure to wind and rain; extreme weather events; intense geological phenomena such as earthquakes, volcano explosions; the ravages of time; destruction as a result of collateral damage in wartimes or as a result of intentional damage, aimed to demoralize and insult the religious and cultural values of an enemy.

Especially in the last century, new factors such as pollution, Climate Change and other human-made factors have taken their toll.

In conservation and restoration, considering aspects such as building technologies, materials, structural issues, preventive measures and restoration strategies, resilience and adaptation methodologies is a really challenging and time-consuming process.

Moreover, the impact of various climatic and other parameters on Cultural Heritage sites is hard to understand and difficult to assess quantitatively and qualitatively due to the limited strategies on Climate Change related issues.

2nd Part **Suggested Title: HYPERION Vision** Storyline (for both narration & subtitles):

The HYPERION EU project, financed by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, aims to provide the appropriate tools in order to better understand the effects of climate change, ravages of time, intense geological phenomena and accidental, extreme weather conditions on archaeological sites and cultural heritage monuments.

3rd Part **Suggested Title: HYPERION Assets** Storyline (for both narration & subtitles):

HYPERION leverages existing novel tools, services and technologies and delivers a brand-new, integrated, resilience assessment platform that will serve as an innovative open-source planning tool.

HYPERION adds on existing tools, by utilizing sensors, including fixed instruments within carefully selected spots in the historic areas, vehicle-based drones, wide-area surveillance services (e.g. Galileo, Copernicus) and even community engagement tools, to arrive at a more comprehensive and synoptic monitoring and emergency response/damage mapping system.

The HYPERION platform includes innovative modelling techniques and advanced machine learning algorithms that maximize the performance and the rapidity of the decision-

making process for addressing multi-hazard risk understanding, better preparedness, faster, adapted and efficient response, and sustainable reconstruction of historic areas.

3rd Part **Suggested Title: HYPERION End Users** Storyline (for both narration & subtitles):

Thus, by using the HYPERION platform, end users will be able to have a better understanding of the dangers and threats to tangible cultural heritage, make decisions for a swifter and more effective response, and contribute to the sustainable re-organisation of the historical regions under threat.

HYPERION addresses policy makers, cultural institutions, municipalities, public authorities, responsible for the management and preservation of national and local tangible cultural heritage assets as well as policy makers, researchers, archaeologists, conservators and other professionals with a key role in conservation-restoration and in safeguarding cultural heritage.

4th Part **Suggested Title: Unique & Social** Storyline (for both narration & subtitles):

HYPERION provides stakeholders with unique benefits that surpass the usual capabilities of decision support systems.

It can perform given damage assessments; a tool that will enable end user training in extreme and unprecedented scenarios, equipping them with the necessary experience to better cope with the unforeseen.

And by using its integrated Pluggable Social Platform for Heritage Awareness and Participation, HYPERION engages local communities and the citizens, mobilising them to identify potential hazards and raise awareness of issues relating to the preservation of regional cultural heritage.

(In this part, PLUGGY logo could pop up together with some animation that will show people using their mobile phones, taking pictures of monuments & upload them in PLUGGY's app, etc. – for more info visit www.pluggy-project.eu)

5th Part

HYPERION will perform extensive tests in four flagship demo sites, in the medieval city of Rhodes island, Greece, in the Albayzín and El Realejo of Granada city, Spain, in Tønsberg, Norway and in Venice, Italy.

6th Part **Suggested Title: Project Facts** No narration, no animation is needed – just presentations

a) Partners: 18 partners from 8 EU countries

b)

Discover more about HYPERION

Project's Coordinator: Dr. Angelos Amditis, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), a.amditis@iccs.gr

Website: www.hyperion-project.eu and QR code (visual)

HYPERION Social Networks

Facebook: @HyperionEUProject

Twitter: @EuHyperion

LinkedIn: @HyperionEUProject

c)

A 4-year EC Funded project

Start date: 1st of June, 2019 HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 821054

APPENDIX 3

SAMPLE SCREENSHOTS FROM THE PARTNERS' WEBSITES

